

Continuous professional development for madrasa teacher professionalism: engaging motivation for engagement

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ABSTRACT

Much research has been done on continuous professional development (CPD) madrasa (Islamic school) teachers, but incorporating motivation of engagement in future professions into them needs to be addressed. This study aims to determine CPD madrasa teachers based on the motivation to engage future professionals in teaching. This research used a phenomenological design involving 16 madrasa Aliyah teachers as informants. Data was collected by interviews with madrasa teachers and analyzed using a systematic design. This research shows that CPD madrasa teachers are related to organizing teaching and learning activities to improve teachers' abilities and competencies in carrying out professional duties and performing as educators. CPD should include skills using digital technology, ethics, and professional values, applying *sharia* principles, *makarim sharia*, and integrity in educating students. Madrasa teachers' view of motivation for engagement in a future profession in CPD refers to the drive that teachers professionals have to continue to be committed to their profession and develop with the changes and demands of the times. The motivation for madrasa teachers' future professional involvement and sustainable professional development is mutually reinforcing. Motivation becomes a driving force for madrasa teachers to engage in CPD, while CPD renews and strengthens madrasa teachers' motivation by providing the skills and knowledge necessary to adapt to future challenges. In this way, motivation and CPD together support better quality education, increase job satisfaction for madrasa teachers, and ensure that teachers remain relevant and competent in facing developments in the world of education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Madrasa education in Southeast Asia has a vital role in shaping the character and intellect of the young Muslim generation [1]. Amid rapid social, economic, and technological changes, madrasa teachers are challenged to remain relevant and practical in teaching [2], [3]. This requires sustainable professional development that can respond to the needs of the times and maintain Islamic values, which are the foundation

of madrasa education [3]–[6]. Continuous professional development (CPD) must be developed to ensure that madrasa teachers can continue to improve their competence and teaching quality [7], [8]. Competent teachers are the key to producing quality graduates ready to face global challenges [9], [10].

CPD is very relevant for madrasa teachers because, in future teaching and profession, it can encourage teacher involvement professionally [4], [5]. However, there is a risk that the CPD of madrasa teachers in the teaching process is often seen as positive and not problematic. This is with the assumption that CPD is observed by the public and other actions that are more passive, such as having a severe and sincere personality in teaching, are not considered a sign of a professional teacher [4], [6], [7]. In addition, the CPD of madrasa teachers and various teacher competencies influence neoliberal trends and are quality measurement factors. These trends can be linked to marketization, focus on performance, individualization, competition, and successful teacher achievement for future employability [8]–[10]. Thus, motivation values for engagement in future professions are urgent for CPD.

Researchers emphasize that the CPD of madrasa teachers involves, for example, teachers who have various competencies, and that is done continuously; teachers can apply the various competencies they have in teaching; and teachers act as agents of educational change in the future development of the teaching profession [11]–[14]. Rich *et al.* [11] underlined that the CPD of teachers, whether in the classroom, in curriculum management, or in the teaching process, can be open to encouraging superior soft skills and have an impact on the success and professionalism of teachers for the future teaching profession, beyond the results that measurable and high achievement. This holistic view is in line with Mlambo *et al.* [14] which emphasizes competence as part of a professional teacher, characterized by community professional abilities, academic professional abilities, leadership professional abilities, and environmental professional abilities.

Other researchers encourage teachers to be CPD and impact curriculum design, necessitating the need to re-examine the role of madrasa teachers, impacting social relations and, thus, hierarchies [15]. In many ways, the CPD of madrasa teachers is based on the teacher's perspective—determining what is important to teachers, what they can teach, and what they can do to achieve the goals set [16]–[19]. The culture of thinking about determining teacher professionalism in teaching at madrasas can hinder the development of CPD of teachers and professional teachers from another perspective. Organizational structure can also be a barrier to the CPD of madrasa teachers. However, there is a need to challenge madrasa teachers to become more professional, a task that advocates continuing professional teacher [16], [19]–[21].

In addition, other researchers examined the CPD of madrasa teachers whose relationship to motivation to work with engagement in teaching can be synthesized in the following aspects: extrinsic, intrinsic, and altruistic. Extrinsic motivation involves teachers' rights to be professional in the learning that affects them, as stated in the CPD of madrasa teacher policies in various countries [22]. Justification for promoting the CPD of madrasa teachers who are compatible with good behavior in cultural diversity [20]. The CPD of madrasa teachers positively impacts school achievement and quality levels, a central factor in quality measurement [23]. However, the positive impact of CPD on madrasa teachers can also be seen as a measurable benefit for the teachers themselves, not only for madrasas. Intrinsic motivation can describe the CPD of madrasa teacher activities in learning that promote their learning, development, and motivation. The justification for promoting the CPD of madrasa teachers is that they must be self-taught, have good morals, and go beyond graduation and completion levels [22], [24]. Opportunities for professionals during the teaching process in madrasas contribute to their understanding and ownership of professionalism [22]. Altruistic motivation can be interpreted as teacher participation in CPD as part of the human educational mission, where teachers learn social attitudes. Teachers are seen as partners committed to learning and practicing the principles of good behavior in the profession [22]–[24].

In fact, the problem of CPD of madrasa teachers so far is that they still need to pay more attention to the integrated motivation of engagement for future professions in their competencies [11]. Not to mention, for example, how to incorporate motivation of engagement for future professions in the assessment process, use of learning methods, and also in the stages of students' self-development [6]–[8]. Moreover, when it comes to sustainable professional development in the future, madrasa teachers are still just starting, without any real action involving motivation or engagement for CPD enforcement in every profession they carry out [11], [13]. This research constructs the CPD of madrasa teachers in teaching, with a focus on the experience of madrasa teachers in teaching at Madrasah Aliyah (Islamic senior high school), Pekanbaru City, Indonesia. CPD of madrasa teachers are defined as teachers who have various Islamic competencies in teaching, impact on school progress, and management of future professional development [3], [5], [11], [25]. So, the research question is:

- i) How is the process of becoming a CPD of madrasa teacher, which focuses on madrasa teaching, defined?
- ii) How can the experience of madrasa teachers regarding the CPD of madrasa teachers in teaching be understood in relation to the motivation of engagement in the future profession of madrasa teachers?

2. METHOD

This research is a phenomenological approach [26] conducted for 1 year at the State Madrasah Aliyah in Pekanbaru City. This study uses an opportunistic selection of informants based on availability [26]. We invited teachers from State Madrasah Aliyah who teach Al-Quran Hadith, *Aqidah Akhlak*, *Fiqh*, and Islamic Cultural History from four State Madrasah Aliyah in Pekanbaru City to participate in this research and 16 teachers from Madrasah Aliyah volunteered. Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 teachers are two men and two women, Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 2 teachers are two men and two women, Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 teachers are three men and one woman, and Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 4 teachers are three women and one man between the ages of 32 and 45 years. During the interview, it was emphasized that this research focused on their experience of professionalism in teaching at madrasahs. The study's number of participants and the background of the study—madrasah teachers in Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia—can be considered limitations of the study.

Data was collected using in-depth interview techniques. In-depth interviews in a phenomenological approach are structured to ensure continuity with researchers [27]; each madrasah teacher participated in a series of five interviews, following the Seidman model [28] and lasting 2–3 hours, focusing on detailed experience and 'reflection on meaning.' The first interview used the narrative of life method and asked the madrasah teacher to reflect on "the definition of a CPD teacher in teaching at the madrasah." The second interview was to identify teachers' experiences with "the benefits and challenges of CPD in teaching at madrasahs." The third interview explored the experience of madrasah teachers about "CPD teachers in teaching understood about the motivation of engagement in future professions to strengthen the madrasah teaching profession for the future."

Thematic analysis was the most suitable method because it examines the holistic meaning of phenomena through the description of subjective perceptions [29]. After transcription of the qualitative data, the transcripts were read repeatedly to be as close to the account as possible. Initial ideas on leading topics and potential themes were recorded using NVivo 13, a qualitative data analysis software. The data is then reread and reviewed to identify possible key ideas that come up repeatedly. Several mind maps were created to understand the nodes' interaction and contextual relationships fully. In the next step, the nodes are combined into the initial code. By considering the node's contextual information, the resulting code is intended to identify the meaning beneath the semantic surface of the data. The data is coded at this stage by categorizing the interview extracts and identifying possible relationships with the CPD madrasah teacher [30]. Initial themes are identified and defined. However, since one of the criticisms of the thematic analysis was that only the identified themes were sought by the researcher, the initial coding and definition of themes were also carried out by the madrasah teacher independently of the researcher. Concordance and difference in coding are contrasted. Comparison between the categorization of the interview extracts of researchers and madrasah teachers and the definition of themes shows high inter-rater reliability. The principal investigator and madrasah teacher coded 76% of the interview extracts either exactly (both raters categorize the text as exact) or equal (both raters categorize the text as including the actual text) to the same two emerging themes. Two themes identified by researchers and madrasah teachers were: i) the definition of CPD madrasah teachers in teaching at madrasah educational institutions and ii) CPD madrasah teachers in teaching in relation to motivation of engagement in future professions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Various understandings of teachers about continuous professional development

The first theme describes the diverse understanding of madrasah teachers about Islamic professional madrasah teachers in the process of future professional development. Islamic professional teachers influence every action taken by teachers based on Islam. The first aspect explains that madrasah teachers express various views on what is meant by the CPD of madrasah teachers. Some madrasah teachers cannot separate the meaning of CPD and their influence on the development of the teaching profession.

"I think the CPD is the process of organizing teaching and learning activities to improve the abilities and competencies of teachers, both pedagogically and professionally, in carrying out my professional duties, as well as performing as an educator and leader for my students." (Informant 4)

"CPD is part of teacher competency development which is carried out according to needs, gradually and continuously to improve professionalism." (Informant 5)

"CPD is essential because it can develop instructional skills and knowledge of the learning content in question." (Informant 1)

CPD of madrasah teachers is related to competence, including and becoming important as teachers. This is exemplified in the following quote:

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“... CPD of madrasa teachers increases teacher competency to achieve competency standards stipulated in applicable laws and regulations... I think continuous professional development meets the needs of teachers and facilitates the development of science, technology, and art.” (Informant 3)

CPD is related to improving the competence of madrasa teachers in learning. CPD is also very important in improving teacher performance in the madrasa education system. CPD is related to professional ability to face the development of educational technology. Some teachers stated that:

“CPD is an important part of the learning process and competency improvement carried out continuously by a professional, to maintain and improve the quality of performance and knowledge in accordance with the demands of the profession.” (Informant 6)

“CPD aims to update, sharpen and expand a professional's abilities to remain relevant and competitive in facing changes in science, technology and the needs and demands of society.” (Informant 14)

For madrasa teachers, CPD is a crucial part of professional development because it is related to personal and professional development. Personal and professional development is needed to acquire new skills so that learning is relevant to the development of the times. Madrasa teachers can develop learning continuously so that the quality of learning improves over time. This is exemplified in the following quote:

“In an educational context, especially for me as a madrasa teacher, CPD includes various activities that support my personal and professional development, such as training, workshops, seminars, research, and independent learning.” (Informant 1)

“For me, this professional development is carried out on an ongoing basis so that teachers are always ready to face changes in the curriculum, teaching methods, student characteristics and the dynamics of education in general.” (Informant 16)

“By taking part in CPD, a madrasa teacher is expected to not only gain new knowledge and skills but also be able to improve the quality of learning in the classroom, develop innovative approaches, and provide a more effective and relevant learning experience for students.” (Informant 8)

The second aspect emphasizes madrasa teachers' understanding of what content is needed as a madrasa teacher in sustainable professional development. Madrasa teachers feel that CPD covers various aspects designed to improve competence, skills and professional attitudes in supporting the learning process. The following quote illustrates the understanding of madrasa teachers regarding motivation for engagement in a future profession as a glue for the CPD madrasa teachers:

“...I always improve my pedagogical competence which includes updating my knowledge and skills in various teaching methods and learning strategies...” (Informant 11)

“CPD includes training in student-centered approaches, such as project-based learning, collaborative learning, and active learning that optimize student participation. For me, CPD should include skills using digital technology and online learning tools that support teaching and evaluation, and the development of social and emotional competencies is very much needed in learning.” (Informant 9)

“This includes skills in building positive relationships with students, managing the classroom with a supportive approach, and creating an inclusive environment.” (Informant 13)

“I believe that CPD is training in conflict management, effective communication, and the empathetic ability to understand students' emotional challenges, which is very important to me as a madrasa teacher. CPD includes increased professional competency and subject matter expertise, classroom management and time management skills, increasing capacity in assessment and evaluation, and research and collaboration based professional development.” (Informant 14)

In contrast to the previous quote, some madrasa teachers also argued that CPD contains ethics and professional values based on *makarim sharia*, teacher career planning, and provides guidance for teacher career development. The content of *makarim sharia* as part of sharia law becomes a reinforcement for madrasa teachers in CPD. Career planning and career guidance are crucial parts of CPD because they

correlate with the progress of future madrasa education. The following quote illustrates the understanding of madrasa teachers regarding CPD content as a glue for madrasa teacher CPD:

“Development of leadership skills for teachers who want to contribute more to the school structure, such as becoming coordinators or group leaders. Includes training in personal time management, effective communication, stress management, and other interpersonal skills that help teachers grow professionally and personally.” (Informant 11)

“Career planning and certification: Help teachers plan a career path that fits their professional aspirations, such as pursuing professional certification, continuing education, or specialization programs.” (Informant 9)

“CPD including provide guidance to achieve further qualifications that can enhance their position or influence in the world of education.” (Informant 6)

3.2. CPD and their relation to motivation for engagement in a future profession

The second theme describes the motivation for engagement in a future profession as a foundation for CPD madrasa teachers in the professional development process. The first aspect relates to madrasa teachers' understanding of motivation for engagement in a future profession and its relation to CPD madrasa teachers. Various answers from madrasa teachers view the relationship between motivation for engagement in a future profession and CPD madrasa teachers.

“Madrasa teachers view motivation for engagement in a future profession in CPD madrasa teachers refers to the drive that teachers or other professionals have to continue to be committed to their profession.” (Informant 2)

CPD madrasa teachers based on motivation for engagement in a future profession, in the understanding of madrasa teachers, as in the following quote:

“For me.... motivation for future professional involvement plays an important role in encouraging me as a madrasa teacher to be actively involved in CPD activities. I have a high commitment to the profession and clear aspirations to develop. I tend to be more enthusiastic about participating in CPD programs because I see it as an opportunity to achieve long-term goals.” (Informant 1)

“This motivation can come from intrinsic factors, such as the desire to become a better educator or fulfill a professional calling. There is also extrinsic motivation, such as career opportunities, promotion, or recognition from the madrasa and the community.” (Informant 16)

In contrast to the previous opinion, other madrasa teachers see CPD based on motivation for involvement in the future profession as a means to achieve goals, external and internal drives that contribute to future quality, and skill enhancement for future progress. This is exemplified in the following quote:

“Here, the teacher must have the ability to analyze Islamic rules in which motivation for engagement in the values of a future profession are constructed in learning.” (Informant 12)

“CPD is understood by madrasa teachers as how a person's internal and external encouragement to continue to contribute to their profession encourages them to participate in ongoing professional development activities actively.” (Informant 15)

“In the educational context, motivation for future professional involvement refers to the desire or commitment of a madrasa teacher to continue to develop and remain relevant in his profession in the long term.” (Informant 10)

“CPD is a process of continuous learning and improving skills carried out by teachers so that they are always ready to face challenges and changes in the world of education.” (Informant 8)

Motivation is very important in the development of CPD of madrasa teachers. Motivation that emerges from madrasa teachers becomes the main glue in the development of future CPD. CPD is not only useful for madrasa teachers themselves, but for the progress of madrasa educational institutions it is important in the future. The quote illustrates the understanding of madrasa teachers regarding motivation for engagement in a future profession as a glue for the CPD madrasa teachers.

“CPD-based motivation for engagement in a future profession is how a madrasa teacher's long-term drive or desire to continue contributing to his profession encourages him to participate in continuous professional development programs or activities.” (Informant 6)

“Motivation for future professional involvement refers to a teacher’s determination, goals, and commitment to develop, adapt, and remain relevant in their profession, even though the world of education continues to change.” (Informant 9)

“This motivation can come from various factors, such as the desire to provide quality teaching, career advancement, or the drive to continue learning and innovating.” (Informant 10)

“CPD is an effort to increase abilities, knowledge, and skills that are carried out periodically and continuously to ensure that teachers remain competent in facing changing educational demands.” (Informant 13)

The second aspect relates to the content of motivation for engagement in a future profession as a basis for CPD madrasa teachers. Motivation as a driving factor in CPD, this is exemplified in the following quote:

“Motivation for future professional involvement plays an important role in encouraging me as a madrasa teacher to be actively involved in CPD activities.” (Informant 7)

“Teachers who have a high commitment to the profession and clear aspirations for development tend to be more enthusiastic about participating in CPD programs because they see it as an opportunity to achieve long-term goals.” (Informant 9)

“This motivation can come from intrinsic factors, such as the desire to become a better educator or fulfill a professional calling. There is also extrinsic motivation, such as career opportunities, promotion, or recognition from the school and community.” (Informant 13)

Another teacher expressed that CPD is a means to achieve future goals, such as the following quote from a madrasa teacher’s experience:

“CPD provides a clear pathway for me to develop the skills and knowledge I need to achieve my long-term goals in the profession. I am motivated to contribute more in the field of education and will see CPD as a concrete step to prepare myself to face future challenges.” (Informant 2)

“By engaging in CPD, I can improve competencies that enable me to take on larger roles or fulfill professional aspirations, such as becoming a leader in a school, teaching at a higher level, or even contributing to education policy.” (Informant 4)

Madrasa teachers perceive that CPD increases motivation by increasing job satisfaction.

“... the participation in CPD allows me to learn new things, face different challenges, and overcome difficulties more effectively...” (Informant 6)

“When I feel competent and ready to face change, my level of job satisfaction increases, which ultimately increases my motivation to continue in this profession.” (Informant 8)

“This increase in satisfaction comes not only from improved technical skills, but also from the ability to manage stress and greater self-confidence in their role as educators.” (Informant 10)

Madrasa teachers who feel successful and growing tend to be more emotionally and professionally involved in their careers.

“CPD supports motivational renewal through continuous learning.” (Informant 12)

“In the dynamic world of education, motivation to engage in the profession can decrease if teachers feel left behind in technological changes or pedagogical developments.” (Informant 14)

“CPD is a means of renewing this motivation by providing up-to-date knowledge and skills. Well-designed CPD can also inspire teachers, opening up insight into the latest educational trends, such as technology-based learning or relevant learning approaches.” (Informant 16)

“In this way, CPD helps teachers stay motivated by providing opportunities to adapt and continue to develop.” (Informant 1)

Madrasa teachers also agree that CPD is the development of motivation to face future challenges, as in the following quote:

“Motivation for future professional involvement for me includes readiness to face challenges that do not currently exist. By taking part in CPD, teachers can prepare themselves for possible curriculum changes, technological developments, or new competency demands in the future.”

Teachers with a long-term vision for their profession's contribution tend to be more open to CPD programs that encourage innovative thinking, mastery of new technologies, and increased skills in educational research. This allows me, as a teacher, to not only keep up with trends, but also lead change in education.” (Informant 5).

CPD for madrasa teachers can improve the quality of teaching and have an impact on professionalism. Several madrasa teachers agreed that:

“Motivation to engage in a future profession also focused on the goal of having a positive impact on students and the educational environment.” (Informant 15)

“CPD provides an opportunity for me to improve the quality of teaching so that it can have a greater impact on student learning.” (Informant 7)

“When I am motivated as a teacher to improve the quality of teaching, I tend to participate in CPD on an ongoing basis, which ultimately improves student learning outcomes and strengthens my confidence in the future teaching profession. So, I have to learn continuously to develop my profession. I love this profession, so I will continue to learn, especially in the era of industrial revolution 5.0 carrying out digital transformation in education and teaching.” (Informant 9)

3.3. Discussion

This research found that the understanding of madrasa teachers varied from that of CPD madrasa teachers. Overall, based on the experience of madrasa teachers, CPD is the process of organizing teaching and learning activities to improve the abilities and competencies of teachers, both pedagogically and professionally, in carrying out professional duties, as well as having performance as an educator and leader for students [9], [31], [32]. The findings of this research illustrate that the CPD of madrasa teachers increases teacher competency and helps them achieve competency standards stipulated in applicable laws and regulations. CPD meets the needs of teachers and facilitates the development of science, technology, and art [11], [12], [31]–[34].

The contents of the competence of CPD in the view of teachers are training in the use of student-centered approaches, such as project-based learning, collaborative learning, and active learning that optimize student participation [18], [19], [31], [35]. CPD should include skills using digital technology and online learning tools that support teaching and evaluation and the development of social and emotional competencies is very much needed in learning [11], [15], [16], [36]. This includes skills in building positive relationships with students, managing the classroom with a supportive approach, and creating an inclusive environment. CPD is training in conflict management, effective communication, and the empathetic ability to understand students' emotional challenges [20], [21], [25]–[27]. CPD includes increased professional competency and subject matter expertise, classroom management and time management skills, increasing capacity in assessment and evaluation, and research and collaboration-based professional development [11], [12], [19].

CPD includes ethics and professional values. For madrasa teachers, this scope includes studying and applying sharia principles, such as *makarim sharia*, which provides for ethical values in Islam and integrity in educating students [21], [22], [24]. Development of leadership skills for teachers who want to contribute more to the school structure, such as becoming coordinators or group leaders. It includes training in personal time management, effective communication, stress management, and other interpersonal skills that help teachers grow professionally and personally [12], [13], [16]–[19]. Career planning and certification help teachers plan a career path that fits their professional aspirations, such as pursuing professional certification, continuing education, or specialization programs. In addition, CPD guides to achieve further qualifications that can enhance their position or influence in the world of education [11], [12], [15], [17].

This research found that CPD madrasa teachers involve motivation for engagement in a future profession madrasa teachers view motivation for engagement in a future profession in CPD madrasa teachers refers to the drive that teachers or other professionals have to continue to be committed to their profession and develop with the changes and demands of the time [19], [20], [31]–[34]. Motivation for future professional involvement is essential in encouraging me as a madrasa teacher to participate in CPD activities. Have a high commitment to the profession and clear aspirations to develop and tend to be more enthusiastic about participating in CPD programs because it as an opportunity to achieve long-term goals [33], [36], [37]. Motivation can come from intrinsic factors, such as the desire to become a better educator or fulfill a professional calling. There is also extrinsic motivation, such as career opportunities, promotion, or recognition from the madrasa and the community [35], [36], [38].

The content of motivation for engagement in a future profession as a basis for CPD madrasa teachers is motivation as a driving factor in CPD. The findings of this research illustrate that motivation for future professional involvement is important in encouraging me as a madrasa teacher to participate in CPD

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activities [34], [35], [37]. Teachers with a high commitment to the profession and clear aspirations for development tend to be more enthusiastic about participating in CPD programs because they see it as an opportunity to achieve long-term goals. This motivation can come from intrinsic factors, such as the desire to become a better educator or fulfill a professional calling. There is also extrinsic motivation, such as career opportunities, promotion, or recognition from the school and community [36], [38], [39].

The findings of this research are strengthened by the opinion which states that CPD is a means to achieve future goals. CPD provides a clear pathway to develop the skills and knowledge needed to reach long-term professional goals. Motivated to contribute more to the field of education and will see CPD as a concrete step in preparing to face future challenges [34], [36]–[39]. Engaging in CPD can improve competencies that enable one to take on more prominent roles or fulfill professional aspirations, such as becoming a leader in a school, teaching at a higher level, or even contributing to education policy. CPD increases motivation by increasing job satisfaction [37], [38]. Participation in CPD allows me to learn new things, face different challenges, and overcome difficulties in a more effective way. The more competent and ready to face change, the higher the level of job satisfaction, which ultimately increases motivation to continue in a profession [39], [40]. This increase in satisfaction comes not only from improved technical skills but also from the ability to manage stress and greater self-confidence in their role as educators.

CPD supports motivational renewal through continuous learning. In the dynamic world of education, motivation to engage in the profession can decrease if teachers feel left behind in technological changes or pedagogical developments [38], [40], [41]. CPD is a means of renewing this motivation by providing up-to-date knowledge and skills. Well-designed CPD can also inspire teachers, opening up insight into the latest educational trends, such as technology-based learning, or relevant learning approaches. CPD helps teachers stay motivated by providing opportunities to adapt and continue to develop. CPD is the development of motivation to face future challenges [39], [41], [42]. Motivation for future professional involvement includes readiness to face challenges that do not currently exist. By taking part in CPD, teachers can prepare themselves for possible curriculum changes, technological developments, or new competency demands in the future [22], [40], [43]–[45]. Teachers with a long-term vision for their profession's contribution tend to be more open to CPD programs that encourage innovative thinking, mastery of new technologies, and increased skills in educational research. This allows me, as a teacher, to keep up with trends and lead change in education [44]–[46].

The findings of this study illustrate that CPD for madrasa teachers can improve the quality of teaching and impact professionalism. Motivation to engage in a future profession also focused on the goal of having a positive impact on students and the educational environment [47]–[49]. CPD provides an opportunity to improve the quality of teaching to have a more significant impact on student learning. When the teacher is motivated to improve the quality of education, they tend to participate in CPD on an ongoing basis, which ultimately improves student learning outcomes and strengthens the confidence in the future teaching profession [45], [47], [48]. Learn continuously to develop the profession, especially in the era of industrial revolution 5.0, carrying out digital transformation in education and teaching [3], [44], [48]–[50].

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude, it is important to acknowledge madrasa teacher's diverse understanding of CPD. Overall, based on the experience of madrasa teachers, CPD madrasa teachers are related to the process of organizing teaching and learning activities to improve the abilities and competencies of teachers, both pedagogically and professionally, in carrying out professional duties, as well as having performance as an educator and leader for students. CPD of madrasa teachers increases teacher competency in achieving competency standards stipulated in applicable laws and regulations. CPD meets the needs of teachers and facilitates the development of science, technology, and art. CPD should include skills using digital technology and online learning tools that support teaching and evaluation, and the development of social and emotional competencies is very much needed in learning. CPD includes ethics and professional values. For madrasa teachers, this scope includes studying and applying sharia principles, such as *makarim sharia*, which provides for ethical values in Islam and integrity in educating students. Madrasa teachers view motivation for engagement in a future profession in CPD. Madrasa teachers refer to the drive that teachers or other professionals have to continue to be committed to their profession and develop with the changes and demands of the times. The motivation for madrasa teachers' future professional involvement and sustainable professional development is mutually reinforcing. Motivation becomes a driving force for madrasa teachers to engage in CPD, while CPD renews and strengthens madrasa teachers' motivation by providing the skills and knowledge necessary to adapt to future challenges. In this way, motivation and CPD together support better quality education, increase job satisfaction for madrasa teachers, and ensure that teachers remain relevant and competent in facing developments in the world of education. This research is still limited to

motivation for engagement in a future profession in developing the CPD of State Madrasah Aliyah teachers, which still allows future research to involve other aspects of Islam and a more comprehensive range of madrasa teachers. Future research can also be developed using a quasi-experimental approach to test the results of research conducted using this qualitative approach.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

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R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **O** Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : **E** Writing - **R**eview & **E**ding

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that we have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The authors state there is no conflict of interest for this manuscript.

INFORMED CONSENT

The protection of privacy is a legal right that must not be breached without individual informed consent. We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study does not use animals as the object of study. This study examines how the involvement of self-efficacy and Islamic psychosocial in building the assessment of Indonesian language teacher learning.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author [ST]. The data, which contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants, are not publicly available due to certain restrictions.

Continuous professional development for madrasa teacher professionalism: engaging ... (Syahraini Tambak)

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